

Addressing data fallacies in undergraduate statistical sciences education

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Abstract

The Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education (GAISE) aim to ensure that learners gain skills to make sense of data. For a variety of reasons, introductory statistics courses mostly use cleaned secondary data. As such, students do not have the experience of formulating questions or determining target populations, measurement methods, or variables. We illustrate the potential pitfalls in analysis and interpretation using case studies of learning materials and practicals. We showcase examples of Simpson's paradox for liberal arts students, and ecological fallacy and the McNamara fallacy for Introduction to Data Science students. To foster active learning, multivariable thinking, and the use of real-life data with purpose and context, we argue the need for the pedagogy of statistical science education to cater to students' curiosity, challenging of assumptions and fostering critical thinking of data. As data become ubiquitous, computational technologies advance, and students pursue increasingly data-driven careers, we need to ensure that curricula emphasize context, statistical theory to inform applications, and the role of subject matter in effective statistics pedagogy.

Key Words: Ecological fallacy, intuition bias, McNamara fallacy, interpretation, Simpson's paradox, undergraduate education.

1. Introduction

Statistical sciences education is at the apex of interdisciplinary scholarship and can consequently be a tool to inform the science literacy levels for global citizens. Statistics is an objective methodological course, and a requirement for almost all undergraduate majors. The use of statistics in other fields of study can never be overemphasized.¹ It equips students with the conceptual tools to work with data.² Statistics are a means to the end of gaining actionable insights, solving real world problems, and gaining informed decisions, premised on the accurate interpretation of the analysis output.³ Interpretation is the translation of statistical analysis output into intelligible descriptions, which is important for countering misinformation.³ Statistical analysis is completed through interpretation, and interpretation proceeds from statistical analysis, hence their interdependence.³ The interpretation of statistical results should be grounded in context and subject matter; however, learned and lived experiences can lead to biases or generate insights. Data fallacy is the problem of incorrectly interpreting data and results. It is a prevalent challenge among the diverse students enrolling in introductory Statistics courses. If left unaddressed, data fallacy can be an impediment to the quality of statistical sciences education and consequently to the practice and profession of statistics. We posit that data interpretation should inform the instructional and assessment processes of undergraduate Statistics courses.

We conducted an observational review to highlight the problem of data fallacy and to proffer recommendations for addressing data fallacy in undergraduate Statistics education. These fallacies can either be intentional abuse of Statistics or unintentional misuse of Statistics.¹ Our review focused on the misuse of Statistics, which is attributed to the user's lack of comprehension.¹ Statistical literacy classes often highlight abuse of Statistics exemplified by media, but nothing on the misuse of statistics by the students.

2. Literature Review

Statistical literacy, reasoning, and thinking are the concepts that inform the framework for statistics education, and the latter two concepts are related but not the same.⁴ The emphasis for statistical reasoning is the comprehension of statistical concepts and making sense of statistical information; and statistical thinking focuses on understanding the how, why and problem context for statistical investigations to aid the evaluation of study findings.⁵ The Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education (GAISE) consist of six recommendations that highlight what needs to be taught and how to teach Statistics. The desired goal of these recommendations is to produce statistically thinking students.⁶ Our research focuses specifically on the first and the third recommendations, because of their connection with the problem of data fallacy. The first recommendation is on teaching statistical thinking, which has been expanded to advocate for teaching Statistics as an investigative process and offer the students the experience to think multivariably. The aim is that statistics teaching keeps up with modern practices and emphasizes advanced computational technologies. Multivariable thinking introduces confounding problems, which are not easily discernible in introductory Statistics learning. Content-centered (*concepts-focused*) learning potentially misses out on problem-centered learning, as it limits critical thinking. Additionally, the third recommendation states the need to integrate real data with context and purpose. This serves to offer students hands-on experience with messy data. This recommendation aims to equip students with data quality skills, contextual comprehension, skills to develop statistical analysis plans, and hypotheses formulation. In-class datasets are often cleaned, limiting the preprocessing and data querying experiences for the learners. Exploratory data analysis (EDA) should inform methodological choice and unit of measurement and analysis. In the presence of ubiquitous data, the centrality of the context of data cannot be overemphasized.⁷ We need pedagogical data sets that are representative of the diverse majors in undergraduate Statistics classes.

In the GAISE recommendations, the concept of data interpretation is somehow not emphasized. Errors can be made in the interpretation, and one such pitfall is that of data fallacy. Data fallacy has long-term consequences for the practice of Statistics. Research has focused on short-term factors influencing Statistics education^{2,8}, but there is a need to develop the skill, care, judgement and objectivity in undergraduate Statistics students for proper interpretation undertaking. Data communication and leadership are vital for addressing real-world problems.

Figure 1: The role of Interpretation in the statistical investigation process

Figure 1 shows that data interpretation bridges the application of statistical methods and the actionable conclusions to solve real-world problems. Interpretation helps to make sense of statistical information, premised on data context and subject matter knowledge from students' majors, readings and collaborative work. The essentials for interpretation are data focused while the precautions in interpretation are a mixture of the essence of data and the interpreter's judgement², with the need to distinguish factual interpretation from personal interpretation. Personal interpretation is often informed from lived and learned experiences. Lived experiences are gained from direct first-hand involvement in everyday events, and learned experiences are from practice, opportunity, and exposure.⁹ These introduce biases and insights based on mindsets and perceptions. Lived and learned experiences feed into an instinct to find causality in everyday events; however, statistics theory is acausal, and experiments are needed to establish causality.¹⁰ The latter informs the fact that Statistics is embedded in conceptual understanding and abstract reasoning.¹⁰ The understanding of statistical concepts informs the competence to use statistical methods and interpret results.¹¹ Students' diverse majors are inherently causal, hence linking these to Statistics can be difficult for learners.¹⁰ For example, mental health problems in universities are often linked to predisposition factors such as basic insecurities; however, the same problem is prevalent in affluent universities, posing a causal link challenge. Perspective transformation helps to change the inherited interpretations from lived and learned experiences.¹²

3. Materials and Methods

We sought to illustrate the problem of data fallacy in the learning of undergraduate Statistics through case studies of learning materials and projects. We observed students' engagement with learning materials and team-based projects on real data. The study population consisted of undergraduate students enrolled in three service Statistics courses. The abductive research framework was employed to solicit for the simplest and most likely conclusions from a set of observations. This serves to generate hypotheses from the assertions based on the students' lived and learned experiences to help improve undergraduate statistical sciences education.

3.1 Case I: Simpson's Paradox

An Introduction to Statistics class consisting of students with diverse majors at a small private liberal arts college was observed for a learning activity. The activity focused on the graphical summarization of quantitative data based on a real-world problem. The data was about the California Department of Development Services (DDS) funding for developmentally disabled individuals. A few years ago, a discrimination lawsuit was filed against the DDS, that claimed that white non-Hispanics were receiving more funding than their Hispanic counterparts. The lawsuit posed serious legal and financial ramifications for the California DDS; hence they hired statisticians to analyze the data to aid their defense.

Figure 2: The visual display for the California DDS Expenditure by Ethnicity

The claim was made based on Figure 2 above, and the students were tasked to substantiate the discrimination claim. Content-centered learning made students concur that there potentially was discrimination since the boxes for the Hispanic and the white non-Hispanics groups did not overlap. There was a sense of achievement and statistical prowess and no conviction for querying beyond the content and concepts learnt. Here is a situation where both the numerical summary statistics and EDA seem to agree on the presence of a difference. The students were encouraged to think about the context of California in terms of demographics and how these could potentially inform the situation better. Refocusing to problem-centered learning, we introduced the concept of data subsetting based on age groups, yielding Figure 3.

Figure 3: Trellis display for data subsetting for California DDS Expenditure by Ethnicity

Upon seeing Figure 3, the students were intrigued, and became curious and inquisitive, foremostly querying what led to Figure 2 being used for the lawsuit basis.

Learned experience informed and guided the students' assessment of the claim. The activity offered a teaching moment on the concept of the Simpson's paradox, that showcases the impact of data aggregation and disaggregation on patterns and trends for associations and relationships between random variables. The statistics investigation process requires that other factors be considered to explain potential disparities, inequities, inequalities, and burdens. The Simpson's paradox reveals the non-immutability of statistical associations beyond what is being controlled. Unlike experiments that incorporate randomization to address bias, observational studies do not allow for conditions to be adjusted for priori. Assessing observational data should be cautious on asserting any association or causal relationship.

3.2 Case II: Unconscious bias

Unconscious bias is attributed to decision-making or concluding without a conscious reasoning process. An Introduction to Statistics class consisting of students with diverse majors at a small private liberal arts colleges went through a video lecture comparing means for total energy expenditure levels between western office workers and an African hunting community.¹² The video offered a different dimension of context to inform the decision and conclusion for the hypothesis testing lecture. The study's conclusion showed insignificant differences in total energy expenditure

between the western office workers and the African hunter gatherers. This was a huge surprise both to the video presenter and to the students thereby showing their own social stereotypes about other groups of people and the consequence of lived experience. This heightened the students' judgement about data and quizzed their data assumptions as their expectations were confounded. The following queries on sedentary lifestyle and obesity in the West and the double burden of malnutrition and harsh living conditions in Africa, and energy allocation versus energy efficiency (*domain knowledge*) informed the students' anticipation for higher mean value for the African hunting community. The emphasis on content and context was reinforced in the teaching to inform hypothesis testing findings.

This lesson served to posit the need for cultural intelligence in statistics education to stem biases and stereotypes due to lived or learned experiences. Global access to data requires that statistical literacy incorporates aspects of diversity and inclusion to inform unbiasedness on viewing data from different cultures. This cements the need for students to be exposed to culturally relevant data in the infancy of statistical science education, while highlighting cultural intelligence for global data literacy.

3.3 Case III: Intuition bias

Intuition bias is premised on the use of mental shortcuts to make decisions that occurs unintentionally and automatically. A statistical literacy class offered for students with diverse majors at a large public R-1 land grant university gave projects based on real-life ethical considerations. One of the projects focused on the privacy-security dilemma presented by the San Bernadino 2015 shooting. The project presented a complex authority-responsibility situation emphasizing data access and management. The situation was between Apple and the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), a private-public conflict. Gut feelings and lived or learned experiences informed the students' decisions on whether privacy would prevail security or vice versa. Sufficient moderation by the instructor facilitated for hearing both sides of the arguments and understanding the philosophy of ethics before asserting one's position. From this project it was learnt that there is need for students to acknowledge the dynamic reality of ethics for data in this rapidly technological advancing world, and to be open to divergent views and convictions, highlighting empathy as a value in the learning of statistical sciences.

3.4 Case IV: McNamara fallacy

McNamara fallacy involves making decisions based on quantitative measures and ignoring all other aspects. An introduction to Data Science class consisting of students with diverse majors at a small private liberal arts college emphasized on in-class labs to synthesize the weekly learnt techniques. In particular, the main takeaway for predictive analytics is the accuracy for future predictions. An in-class lab focused on regression modeling as a supervised Machine Learning technique. Machine learning theory focuses on accuracy while statistical theory accounts for regression modeling focuses on parsimony, diagnostics, and goodness of fit metrics for model development. Accuracy is a quantitative measure while diagnostics and parsimony are qualitative attributes for model selection. The learning objective of parsimony is to obtain simple models, on the contrary accuracy metrics improves with increase in the complexity of the model. The issue of the definition of a simple model or complex model is subjective outside of the underlying statistical theory. The McNamara fallacy offers a preponderance of quantitative metrics over the qualitative measures on decision-making. When investigating quantitative data, students tend to drift to the much-touted accuracy metrics in contrast to the qualitative attributes of diagnostics and parsimony in determining the best fit model. Under this metric bias, that can be attributed to the learned experience of the students, spurious models and gloating over multicollinearity in pursuit of high accuracy metrics and accurate predictions inform the best fit model selection. This case exemplified the need to acknowledge the roles of subject matter in the learning of statistics, and statistical theory in statistical applications. To address the quantitative-qualitative attributes contributions, we allowed for the students to learn from their pitfalls by requiring them to offer justifications for their selected models. We further emphasized to the students the need to balance between the quantitative and qualitative aspects for the best fit model selection.

One of the talking points on Data Science education is on the amount of statistical theory in the curriculum to inform the computational algorithms that are being developed and implemented for predictive analytics. The McNamara fallacy is a real Data Science problem especially when statistical theory is not emphasized; hence, there is a need to moderate Data Science education to preserve it from being labeled a Blackbox initiative.

3.5 Case V: Ecological fallacy

An introduction to Data Science class consisting of students with diverse majors at a small private liberal arts college offers a deep dive into learning from real world data. A major highlight of the end of Spring semester is the university media's article on the summaries of GPA data for the graduating class overall, and for the excelling majors. A Fall semester class activity on how such data can be used to inform the marketing and admission department was presented. The goal was to make sense of data and offer actionable information.

The problem focused on how these data could be used to offer a basis for recruitment of a freshman class. An ecological fallacy stems from the uncritical use of summary statistics, where findings at the group-level are translated to individual level.¹³ The challenge of the over-reliance on the use of summary statistics to describe and analyze inequalities is a reality as exemplified by the California DDS expenditure lawsuit in case I, above. Passion-driven commitment, a consequence of both the lived and learned university norms, tends to override concepts in how students interpret the grouped data summaries to individual level inference. This is a consequence of misunderstanding the unit of analysis. At the center of this assessment are data communication and the skill to convert quantitative information into qualitative business solutions. The challenge of translating group-level data to individual-level is prevalent in the practice of Statistics.

From this lesson, it was learned that the instruction of statistical concepts in Data Science should offer a critical review of how summary statistics should be interpreted and the need to distinguish between group-level and individual level analysis. The teaching on measures of center, spread, and position, should be clear on the level of measure to inform their interpretation in the practice of Statistics.

To address the challenge of ecological fallacy, the Introduction to Data Science curriculum should emphasize the contributions of within group variation, confounding factors, sample size effect, and adjustment for individual differences in interpreting summary statistics.

4. Discussion

The five case studies above showcased the reality of data fallacy in the learning of undergraduate statistical sciences. The students' lived and learned experiences seemed to inform the fallacies and biases. We propose that an instrument in the form of a pre- and post-quiz be developed to measure data fallacy in undergraduate statistical sciences education. This will serve to measure the extent of data fallacy and the impact of Statistics learning on addressing it and to identify associated factors. There is a need for using culturally relevant data in introductory classes to help alleviate biases and social stereotypes. Undergraduate statistical science syllabi should incorporate quotes on mistakes, and these should be emphasized in the learning process.

Examples: Mistakes are the portals of discovery. James Joyce

Each life is made up of mistakes and learning, waiting and growing, practicing patience and being persistent. Billy Graham

If you're not making mistakes, then you're not doing anything. I'm positive that a doer makes mistakes. John Wooden

Failure is a great teacher, and I think when you make mistakes and you recover from them and you treat them as valuable learning experiences, then you've got something to share. Steve Harvey.¹⁴

Practicing and experiencing data interpretation with peers, creating a culture or environment for growth mindset (continuous mental growth and development), and engaging in collaborative

learning are essentials for gaining the skill of data interpretation. Misinterpretation impacts real-world decisions in healthcare policy, business, and computing and engineering systems.

We further recommend that there is a need to review statistical sciences student assessments in terms of what proportion data interpretation should constitute. The GAISE recommendations advance statistical thinking, and we are proposing that statistical reasoning, which informs data interpretation, should be equally considered. That will help promote the effective practice and profession of Statistics in the real world and hence counter misinformation.

The phenomenon of data fallacy showcases how lived and learned experiences affect the interpretation of statistical results. These experiences can potentially stimulate Justice, Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (JEDI)-oriented research in the teaching and learning of undergraduate statistics education. As we work to diversify the statistics community and provide inclusive instruction in statistics, we need to be aware of and understand how lived and learned experiences affect interpretation. Further, specific pedagogical tools (e.g., facilitated class discussions) can help students become aware of how their own lived and learned experiences are affecting their interpretation and how others' such experiences can lead to differing interpretations. They can also offer experiences that build students' skills in finding consensus on interpretations. There is need to address how diverse students can be inspired, how statistics teaching can be adapted to diverse learning needs, and how establishing a supportive and engaging learning environment, while emphasizing pedagogical rigor, can be informed and implemented. Peer-led learning, data debates, and simulations to promote statistical reasoning are pedagogical methods that can help reduce data fallacies.

5. Conclusion

Data fallacy impacts Statistics in real life in terms of both the practice and the profession. We conclude that statistical interpretation is an essential skill that should be honed through learning practice and experience. The GAISE recommendations should consider statistical reasoning as a prerequisite for the goal of statistically thinking students. Statistics education should emphasize data communication as an essential soft skill to inform data/statistical leadership in the real world and across students with different majors. Utilizing culturally relevant data can help to address inequalities, inequities, and biases attributed to data fallacies. The latter concerns offer a platform to explore JEDI goals in the teaching of undergraduate Statistics.

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